

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: POLICY PERSPECTIVE

Mr. Padmanabha C.H

Assistant Professor, College of Education, Srinivas University, Mangalore

Email: haipadmanabha@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Inclusive is receiving–children with exceptionalities in the mainstream. There are a variety of aspects such as structural, historical, and religious factors, which shape the course of special education, inclusion, and the development of legislation and policies in India. With the experience of a complicated history and social structure, the emergence efforts of India towards special education, particularly the inclusive policy are fairly significant. Inclusive education programmes do not focus on the accommodation of these children into general school education setting, but are focused on the restructuring of schools to accept and provide for the needs of students. Some education commissions like the Kothari Commission in the year 1964 said that for educational opportunity of children with special needs, educational facilities should be extended to four categories of children with special needs such as the blind, the deaf, the orthopedically handicapped, and the mentally retarded. Few years later, the Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment, Government of India, initiated the IEDC programme to promote the integration of children with mild and moderate disabilities into regular schools. The programme was intended to include children with disabilities into mainstream classroom with financial support, special equipment, and aids. For the development of inclusive education, there are various policies and constitutional issues drafted in the form of laws or acts. These acts/ laws provide basic guidelines to every teacher on how best way one can treat these individual differences among children.-With globalization, policy issues related to inclusive education took a different direction after independence. The present research paper highlights the different policies of Inclusive education and how best a teacher can contribute to the welfare of these children.Itis extremely useful for teacher educators, school teachers, child right activists, and social thinkers.

Keywords: Inclusive education, Historical development, PWD Act, RTE Act.

Introduction

Inclusive education is educating all students in age-appropriate general education classes in neighborhood schools, with high quality instruction, interventions, and support so that they can

“Contemporary Issues and Challenges of Teacher Education”

flourish in the core curriculum. Inclusive schools have a collaborative and respectful school culture where students with disabilities are presumed to be competent, develop positive social relationships with peers, and are fully participation members of the school community. Inclusive education has grown from the belief that education is a basic human right and that it provides the foundation for a more just society. All learners have a right to education, regardless of their individual characteristics or difficulties. Inclusive education initiatives often have a particular focus on those groups, which, in the past, have been excluded from educational opportunities. These groups include children living in poverty, those from ethnic and linguistic minorities, girls (in some societies), children from remote areas, and those with disabilities or other special educational needs. The latter are often the most marginalized both within education and in society in general.

Definition

Inclusive education has been defined by Dukes & Lamar-Dukesas “all students being educated where they would be educated if they did not have a disability (i.e., in age appropriate general education classes in their neighborhood school) with necessary supports provided to students, educators, and families so that all can be successful”. Paul Collins, of the University of Rochester has stated. “The inclusion model has gained a wide prominence in the field of education very quickly, yet the model remains ill-defined in its implementation and practice”. These are the principles that guide quality inclusive education.

History of Inclusive Education

The historical move of India from special education towards inclusive education and the development of policy and legislations can be comprehended by focusing on pre-independence and post-independence era.

Pre-independence

In 1869, the very first formal school for children with disabilities was started by Jane Leupot with the help of the Church Missionary Society for “blind students” in Benares. In 1918, in the eastern part of India, the first school for children with intellectual and physical disabilities was established in Kurseong.

Post-independence

After independence, the Government of India created many policies for education. In 1960, the

“Contemporary Issues and Challenges of Teacher Education”

Ministry of Education was divided and a new branch called “The Ministry of Social Welfare” was created and given the responsibility for the “weak and vulnerable” sections of the society.

The Education Commission (1964-66)

Popularly, known as the Kothari Commission,. For the first time the history of Indian education favored making education of the handicapped an integral part of the general education system. Furthermore, the Kothari Commission recommended a cell at NCERT to study the work being done in the field of education for the handicapped in the country and abroad and to prepare material for the teachers. However, due to various reasons, the Government of India failed to implement it. But to some extent, the Kothari Commission was able to successfully implement the Integrate Child Development Scheme (ICDS). The ICDS reached out to the “vulnerable populations” to provide service such as healthcare, nutrition, and pre-school facilities and early intervention to children below five years of age.

The Integrated Education for Disabled Children (1964)

The Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment, Government of India, initiated the IEDC programme to promote the integration of children with mild and moderate disabilities in regular schools. It was intended to include children with disabilities in mainstream classroom with the financial support, special equipment, and aids. It provided one special teacher for every eight children with disabilities and was partly funded by UNICEF, while fifty per cent of the funding was supposed to be carried out by the state governments. The responsibility was transferred to the Department of Education in the year 1992.

National Policy on Education (1986)

This particular policy was acting as a guide to the education system in India under its broad objectives of ‘education for equality’. Continuing in the spirit of the 1974 IEDC, the NPE asserted that children with “mild” disabilities should be included in the mainstream classroom, whereas children with “moderate to severe” disabilities should be educated in segregated schools. NPE devoted specific measures for students with disabilities such as vocational training for the disabled. Voluntary efforts for the education of the disabled were encouraged. Teacher training was provided for all mainstream education teachers by “including compulsory special education component in pre-service training of general teachers”.

“Contemporary Issues and Challenges of Teacher Education”

The Rehabilitation Council of India Act, 1992

It was established by The Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment. The council was formed to standardize training courses for professionals dealing with persons with disabilities; To prescribe minimum standards of education and training of various categories of professionals/personnel dealing with people with disabilities; To promote research in Rehabilitation and Special Education; and To maintain Central Rehabilitation Register for registration of professionals/ personnel. In the year 1992, the Indian Government established a rehabilitation council.

Persons with Disabilities (Equal Opportunities, Protection of Rights and Full Participation) Act, 1995

The Parliament enacted the Persons with Disabilities (Equal Opportunities, Protection of Rights and Full Participation) on 7th February 1996. The Act desired that appropriate governments and local authorities. Should ensure that, every child with disability had access to free education in an appropriate environment until he attained the age of 18 years. It also made provision for the reservation of at least 3% seats in the educational institutions for persons with disabilities. The Act listed seven categories of disability such as Blindness, Low vision, Leprosy-cured, Hearing impairment, Loco motor disability, Mental retardation, and Mental illness. One major initiative that took birth out of the PWD Act was the advent of the District Primary Education Programme (DPEP), a joint initiative of the Indian Department of Education, Government of India, and the World Bank. The DPEP focused on inclusion of children with mild to moderate disabilities. The most important part of this programme included Teacher Training through the District Institutes of Education (DIETs), following the Persons with Disability Act.

The National Trust for Welfare of Persons with Autism, Cerebral Palsy, Mental Retardation and Multiple Disabilities Act, 1999

This landmark legislation came into existence in 1999. Its objectives are: To enable and empower persons with disability to live as independently and as fully as possible within and as close to their community as possible; To facilitate the realization of equal opportunities, protection of rights and full participation of persons with disability; and To extend support to its registered organizations to provide need based services.

Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan: “Education for All”.

RTE mandates free and compulsory education to all children from 6-14 years of age. The key

“Contemporary Issues and Challenges of Teacher Education”

objective of RTE- SSA is the Universalization of Elementary Education (UEE). Three important aspects of UEE are access, enrolment, and retention of all children in 6-14 years of age. This goal of UEE has further been facilitated by the Constitutional (86th Amendment) Act, making free and compulsory elementary education a Fundamental Right, for all the children in the age group of 6-14 years. This Amendment has given a new thrust to the education of Children with Special Needs (CWSN), as without their inclusion, the objective of UEE cannot be achieved. In fact, inclusion of one of the groups, which is extremely crucial for UEE, is perhaps that of the CWSN. Hence, education of CWSN is an important component of SSA.

Provisions for CWSN under SSA

SSA provides up to Rs.3000/- per child for the inclusion of disabled children, as per specific proposal, per year. District plan for children with special needs is formulated within the Rs.3000/- per child norm, with Rs. 1000/- earmarked exclusively for engagement of resource teachers. The interventions under SSA for inclusive education are identification, functional and formal assessment, appropriate educational placement, preparation of Individualized Educational Plan, provision of aids and appliances, teacher training, resource support, removal of architectural barriers, research, monitoring and evaluation, and a special focus on girls with special needs.

RTE- SSA’s Policy on Inclusion

Policy interventions- SSA ensures that every child with special needs, irrespective of the kind, category, and degree of disability, is provided meaningful and quality education. Hence, SSA has adopted a *zero rejection policy*. This means that no child having special needs should be deprived of the right to education and taught in an environment, which is best suited to his/her learning needs. These include special schools, EGS, and even home-based education for inclusive children. Every child with special needs should be placed in the neighborhood school, with needed support services. Children with special needs need to be facilitated to acquire certain skills that will enable them to access elementary education as envisaged in the Act. For instance, they may need mobility training, training in Braille, sign language, postural training, etc. Thus, school attentiveness of children with special needs must be made sure by providing ‘special training’ as predicted in the RTE Act. This training may be residential, non-residential or even home- based, as per their specific requirements. The existing non form a land alternate schooling (including home-based education) options for children with disabilities can be recast as ‘special training’. This means that

“Contemporary Issues and Challenges of Teacher Education”

(a) all children with special needs who are not enrolled in schools or have dropped out, will first be enrolled in a neighborhood school in an age appropriate grade, and (b) they will be entitled to ‘special training’ through regular teachers or teachers specifically appointed for the purpose.

Thus, SSA has adopted a more expansive and a broad-based understanding of the concept of inclusion, wherein a multi-option model of educating CWSN is being implemented. The dual objective of implementation is to bring more CWSN under the umbrella of SSA and to provide to CWSN appropriate need based skills, be it vocational, functional literacy or simply activities of daily living. Further, an attempt is being made to provide these skills in the most appropriate learning environment.

The Right to Education Act was drafted in 2005 by the Ministry of Human Resource and Development. This bill was framed through a “social justice and collective advocacy perspective” and is not disability specific, but is inclusive of children with disabilities with specific sections that address the educational rights of students of disabilities. It was passed in 2009 and came into forces in 2010. Every child between the ages of 6 to 14 years has the right to free and compulsory education. This is stated as per the 86th Constitution Amendment Act via Article 21A. The Right to Education Act seeks to give effect to this amendment.

Rights of Persons with Disabilities Bill, 2016

The bill .repeals the Persons with Disabilities (Equal Opportunities, Protection of Rights and Full Participation) Act of 1995.**Salient Features:**

Definition of disability: Disability has been defined based on an evolving and dynamic concept. The types of disabilities have been increased from existing 7 to 21 and the Central Government will have the power to add more types of disabilities. In the year 2016, total 21 kinds of disabilities were added; The 21 disabilities are given below:

1. Blindness,
2. Low-vision,
3. Leprosy cured persons,
4. Hearing Impairment (deaf and hard of hearing),
5. Locomotors disability,
6. Dwarfism,
7. Intellectual disability,

“Contemporary Issues and Challenges of Teacher Education”

8. Mental illness,
9. Autism spectrum disorder,
10. Cerebral palsy,
11. Muscular dystrophy,
12. Chronic neurological conditions,
13. Specific learning disabilities,
14. Multiple sclerosis,
15. Speech and language disability,
16. Thalassemia,
17. Haemophilia,
18. Sickle cell disease,
19. Multiple disabilities including deaf blindness,
20. Acid attack victim, and
21. Parkinson's disease.

It also defines persons with benchmark disabilities as those with at least 40% of any of the above specified disabilities.

Speech and Language Disability and Specific Learning Disability have been added for the first time.

Acid Attack Victims have been included.

Dwarfism and muscular dystrophy have been indicated as separate class of specified disability. The new categories of disabilities also included three blood disorders, viz., Thalassemia, Hemophilia, and Sickle Cell disease.

Rights of Persons with Disabilities

Persons with disabilities (PwDs) shall have the right to equality. They shall not be discriminated against on grounds of their disability. Their rights include protection from inhuman treatment and equal protection and safety in situations of risk, humanitarian emergencies, natural disasters, and armed conflict. All existing public buildings shall be made accessible for disabled persons.

Education and Skill Development

It provides for access to inclusive education, self-employment, and vocational training to disabled persons. At least 5% seats in all government institutions of higher education and those getting aid

“Contemporary Issues and Challenges of Teacher Education”

from the government are required to reserve seats for persons with benchmark disabilities. Earlier it was only 3%.

Conclusion

Every nation thrives for the betterment of society, policies helps us to improve life expectancies, Inclusive education is one of such important disciplines in day to days life, helps us to understand better, feel better towards humanity. There was no concept like inclusion during pre-independent period that means it is not like our country don't have disability. Disability was practiced even before independence but due to various constraints, resources. The government of India does not draft policies. But after independence, we can see many changes in disable education; Therapeutic concepts are also improving in fields like speech and hearing, audiology, and occupation therapist. These disciplines further help to bring more improvements in their life. The Supreme Court of India also delivered some important landmark verdicts in the area of disability. .By understanding these basic concepts, one can participate effectively in any democratic country. Further, it helps towards progress and social change.

Bibliography

- 1) Mustafa K.M. & Goerge Jibin (2016). A.P.H. Publishing Corporation, New Delhi-110002.
- 2) Puri Madhumitha & Abraham George (editor) (2004).Handbook of inclusive education for educators, administrators and planners, within walls without boundaries. Sage Publication, New Delhi.
- 3) Dash, Neena (2006). Inclusive education for children with special needs. Atlantic Publishers and Distributors (P) Ltd., New Delhi-110027.
- 4) Gupta, Neeru (2017). Major issues and challenges in special education in India. Horizon Books (A division of Ignited Minds Education Pvt. Ltd.).
- 5) Gupta, K. Arun, Gupta, Renu, Tandon & Bharti (2018). Implementing inclusion in schools. Notion Press Publication, Chennai-60013.
